

Editorial

Cybercrime Monitoring System for Online Security Experts

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Cybercrime Monitoring System for Online Security Experts

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Abstract: Cyberspace is increasingly attacked and there are limited means of mitigating this act. This is usually due to a shifted degree of security attributes and management schemes within the cloud entity in cyberspace. The challenges are due to improvements in methods and the utilisation of new technologies in committing crimes by cybercriminals. The threat of cybercrime will continue to evolve and grow as cybercriminals adapt to new security solutions and take advantage of the changes in online behaviour. Hence, it is still challenging to identify and track down cyber criminals. This study focuses on implementing a cybercrime monitoring system for online data experts. After an in-depth understanding of cyber users' attacks, a possible solution is proposed. A web application portal is designed using WordPress development tools that will serve as a platform to monitor and present possible vulnerabilities discovered. Tawk.to is integrated into the website for the implementation of real-life monitoring and My Structured Query Language (MySQL) is used as the database for storing and retrieval of information. This system captures the digital signature of each piece of information sent to cyberspace, the user login parameter, date, time, the location of the user, the Media Access Control address of the system used, and activities carried out by the user while online. It also aids cyber security experts in ascertaining the extent of activities carried out by cybercriminals in the domain. The outcome demonstrated that the system could identify cyber users and their activities online.

Key Words: Cybercrime, Cyberspace, Cyber Criminals, Security Expert

I. INTRODUCTION

Security of life and property is very vital to human life. Human life needs to be protected from critical and pervasive threats. The rate of security threats in the world is increasing at an exponential rate (Walker-Roberts *et al.*, 2020). Due to this challenge, individuals and governments have designed means to safeguard and protect themselves and their citizens against such threats. These security threats may include physical and cybercrime threats (Chatfield & Reddick, 2019).

Crime is a major issue in the world today. One of the factors influencing crime incidents is the technological advancement we are experiencing globally (Sadiku *et al.*, 2022). Burglary, internet crime, theft, and fraud are all examples of crime. Typically, criminal behaviour is motivated by greed, rage, jealousy, retaliation, or pride, which negatively impacts other law-abiding citizens (Paul & Aithal, 2018). Also, committing a crime can result in the dissolution of an organisation's structure and governance, which necessitates the implementation of security measures in every aspect of our lives. Cybersecurity is essential for containing this threat.

Cyber security plays an important role in Information

Technology (IT). In the modern day, information protection has grown to be a major issue. Cybersecurity has grown to be a significant issue in the information technology (IT) industry during the past ten years. Cybercrime causes a lot of issues for people, organisations, and the government, and many steps are being made to combat it. Notwithstanding these precautions, there are still concerns about cyber security because a cybercrime attack can result in anything from widespread fraud to the blackmail of major corporations (Kalakuntla *et al.*, 2019).

A crime that involves a computer and a network is referred to as cybercrime (Agana & Inyama, 2015). It's possible that the computer was used in the crime or that it was the subject of a cyberattack. A concerted attack on a computer system to touse hardware operations, alter processing control, or corrupt stored data can be described as a computer attack (Aiken *et al.*, 2022). Cybercrime is the term used to describe any crime perpetrated through computer networks. These crimes are done against specific people or groups of people to damage the victim's reputation, either directly or indirectly. This is done with the use of advanced media transmissions systems such as the Internet, trojan, hacking, phishing, website cloning, copyright infringement and many more. The rate at which cybercrime is growing in the current environment is concerning and has increased security threats (Prakash *et al.*, 2019). Cybercrime investigation is a very challenging process since it is challenging to identify or track cybercrime perpetrators. Criminals have used computers and the internet to conduct crimes while remaining anonymous (Javed *et al.*, 2022). To safeguard users from cyberterrorism, computer-based monitoring systems are required. These systems make it simple to record evidence of hackers who infiltrate a network. It is worth noting that cybercrime has been of great benefit to its Practitioners and their benefactors. While it has been dysfunctional to the victims of the scammers, their dependents, and to a large extent society, it has become an image nightmare for most countries and their citizens. With the Internet creating limitless opportunities for commercial, social, and educational activities today, many businesses and personal transactions are conducted electronically. For this reason, cybercrime must be taken seriously by industry experts and academics at large.

This study focuses on developing a cost-effective model of a cybercrime monitoring system for online security experts. The specific objectives of the study are to develop a navigable and usable website suitable for monitoring threats, integrate Tawk.to to the website and evaluate the performance of the system.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Cybercrime is challenging because of the shifted degree of security attributes and management schemes within the cloud entity in cyberspace (Agana & Inyama, 2015). The threat

posed by cybercrime will continue to evolve and grow as criminals adapt to new security solutions and take advantage of the changes in online behaviours (Eddolls, 2016). Additionally, because of the nature of cybercrime, which is domiciled in cyberspaces, it is difficult for law enforcement to identify and bring cybercriminals to justice (Rogers & Seigfried, 2004). Although several cyber monitoring systems have been in existence, it is still difficult to identify and track cybercriminals. The problem is the cost implication and difficulty in integrating a Web Application Firewall into a website (Mihai, 2017). Also, monitoring large user groups is tedious (Ba, 2017). The humongous cost and difficulty in implementing an automated monitoring device discourage individuals and organisations from effectively monitoring their websites. As a result, Cybercrime continues to increase. This has raised concerns. This study is work-in-progress research that will aid in monitoring internet users' actions, the recovery of digital proof of cybercrime, and the protection of users from hacking.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

After determining and understanding how users are attacked online, a suitable method and methodology for developing an enhanced Cyber Crime Monitoring System for Online Security Expert is implemented. A web application portal is designed using WordPress development tools that will serve as a platform to monitor the activities of users visiting the web Gateway. Tawk.to API is integrated into the website for the implementation of a real-life Monitoring System, and MySQL is used as the database for the storage of information of users that visits the website. This application will keep track of a user's online activity and index.dat file content by taking screenshots, allowing online security professionals to better defend their domain.

This system will record the digital signatures of every piece of information transferred into cyberspace, the user's login credentials, the user's geographic location, the MAC address of the computer they are using, the date, time, and the actions they took online. It will support forensic professionals' investigations and efforts to catch cybercriminals.

Figure 1: System Architecture

A. Research Method

The research methods adopted in this study are as follows:

1. Software Development: A navigable and usable website is developed using WordPress development tools and PHP is used as the programming language. MySQL database is integrated into the website for storage of information of users that visit the website. Tawk.to is integrated into the website for proper monitoring.
2. Experiment: In this phase, all the components of the system are tested to ascertain the aim of the study.
3. Evaluation: The System Usability Scale is adopted for the evaluation performance of the system. It is a standardised survey-based method for the assessment of perceived usability. The questionnaire is distributed to twenty (20) participants to get their feedback about the functionality of the system. The usability of a system takes the level of satisfaction, effectiveness and efficiency into consideration. While the usability test is carried out because of the user, the outcome of the test is focused on the system and not the user (Sakpere *et al.*, 2017).

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

A temporary website is designed and hosted online which serves as the platform to be monitored. The monitoring dashboard is launched which pops up a login page. On the login page, the administrator enters a username and password to gain access to the system. The administrator was able to view two users on the website and the actions they are carrying out while online. The system was able to capture the location of the users and the Media Access Control address of the system used, and any suspected user would be immediately banned from the website. The website is developed to serve as a platform in which the activities would be easily monitored. It is structured in four categories to present information about:

- Cybercrime Monitoring System
- Monitor Control Login
- WordPress Admin
- Developer

Figure 2: The research website

Figure 3: Cybercrime Monitoring Dashboard Login Portal

The Cybercrime Monitoring Dashboard Login Portal as shown in Figure 3, is the screenshot system login page. The login page contains two basic and necessary information, the username and password to have access to the system. The

username is the name of the administrator or any user authorised or allowed to gain access to the application, while the password is used to verify the identity of the user during the authentication procedure.

Figure 4: Three users detected on the Monitoring System

Figure 5: User Location and IP Address Detected

Three users were detected on the monitoring system as shown in Figure 4, the administrator was able to view three users on the website and the actions they are carrying out while online. Screenshot of the User Location and IP address detected as shown in Figure 5. The system was able to capture the location of the users and the Media Access Control address of the system used, and any suspected user would be immediately barred from the website.

V. EVALUATION

Software testing is an inspection done to tell stakeholders about the calibre of the software product or service that is

being tested. Product testing can also give an objective, unbiased impression of the software, enabling the business to recognise and understand the risks related to the adoption of software. The testing technique is the act of running a programme or application to find software bugs (errors or other problems) and confirm that the software is suitable for usage (Cayola & Macías, 2018). After the completion of the system, Unit testing was carried out to check the functionality of each component of the system to know if the component is integrated as planned. The whole system testing was done when all the modules had been successfully integrated and tested. System testing made sure that the requirements and design complied.

A. Performance Evaluation

The performance evaluation of the system is done using System Usability Scale (SUS). SUS is a standardised questionnaire-based method for the assessment of perceived usability. It has proven to be quick but not dirty (Lewis, 2018). SUS was developed by John Brooke in the year 1996. It demonstrated how urgently the usability community needed a tool to get consumers' subjective ratings of a product's usability (Bangor *et al.*, 2008).

B. Evaluation using the System Usability Scale

The evaluation questionnaire was given to twenty (20) participants to get their feedback about the usability of the application. SUS is used to determine the level of satisfaction, effectiveness and efficiency. SUS consists of ten (10)

standardised questions based on a 4-point Likert Scale where Strongly Disagree = 1, Disagree = 2, Agree = 3, and Strongly Agree = 4.

SUS uses a complex scoring system because it comprises five (5) positive odd-numbered questions and five (5) negative even-numbered questions. SUS score = $(X + Y) * 2.5$, where X = Add up the total score of all odd-numbered questions then subtract 5.

Y = Add up the total score of all even-numbered questions then subtract from 25.

$$\text{Average} = \frac{\sum \text{ of all SUS Scores}}{\text{Number of Participants}}$$

C. SUS Scores for Participants of the Cybercrime Monitoring System

Table 1: SUS Score for Users of the Cybercrime Monitoring System Using 4-Point Likert Scale

Users	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	SUS Score	NPS
1	4	1	3	1	3	1	4	1	4	1	87.5	Promoter
2	4	1	4	2	4	2	4	2	4	1	80.0	Passive
3	4	1	3	2	4	2	4	1	4	1	80.0	Promoter
4	3	1	4	2	4	1	4	1	4	1	82.5	Promoter
5	4	1	4	1	4	1	4	1	4	1	87.5	Promoter
6	4	1	4	2	4	1	3	1	3	2	77.5	Passive
7	4	1	4	1	4	1	4	1	4	1	87.5	Promoter
8	4	2	4	1	4	2	4	1	4	1	82.5	Promoter
9	3	1	4	2	4	2	4	2	4	2	75.0	Passive
10	4	1	3	2	3	1	4	2	3	2	72.5	Passive
11	4	2	4	2	3	1	4	1	4	2	77.5	Passive
12	3	1	4	2	4	2	3	2	4	1	75.0	Passive
13	4	2	4	1	4	2	4	1	4	1	82.5	Promoter
14	3	1	3	1	4	2	4	2	3	1	75.0	Passive
15	4	1	4	1	3	1	3	1	4	2	80.0	Promoter
16	4	1	3	2	4	1	4	1	4	1	82.5	Promoter
17	4	1	3	1	4	1	4	1	4	1	85.0	Passive
18	4	1	4	1	4	2	4	1	3	1	82.5	Promoter
19	3	1	4	1	4	1	4	2	4	1	82.0	Promoter
20	3	1	4	1	4	1	4	1	4	2	82.5	Passive

User 1 = 87.5, User 2 = 80.0, User 3 = 80.0,
 User 4 = 82.5, User 5 = 87.5, User 6 = 77.5,
 User 7 = 87.5, User 8 = 82.5, User 9 = 75.0,
 User 10 = 72.5, User 11 = 77.5, User 12 = 75.0,
 User 13 = 82.5, User 14 = 77.5, User 15 = 80.0,
 User 16 = 82.5, User 17 = 85.0, User 18 = 82.5,
 User 19 = 85.0, User 20 = 82.5

Sum of all SUS Scores for all Participants = 87.5 + 80.0 + 80.0 + 82.5 + 87.5 + 77.5 + 87.5 + 82.5 + 75.0 + 72.5 + 77.5 + 75.0 + 82.5 + 75.0 + 80.0 + 82.5 + 85.0 + 82.5 + 82.0 + 82.5 = 1617

$$\text{The Average SUS score} = \frac{1617}{20} = 80.9$$

$$\text{Average} = \frac{\sum \text{ of all SUS Scores}}{\text{Number of Participants}}$$

Figure 6: Percentile Ranking for Common SUS Scores

Table 2: Percentiles, Grades, Adjectives, and NPS Categories to Describe Raw SUS Scores

Grade	SUS	Percentile Range	Adjective	Acceptable	NPS
A+	84.1 – 100	96 – 100	Best Imaginable	Acceptable	Promoter
A	80.8 – 84.0	90 – 95	Excellent	Acceptable	Promoter
A-	78.9 – 80.7	85 – 89		Acceptable	Promoter
B+	77.2 – 78.8	80 – 84		Acceptable	Passive
B	74.1 – 77.1	70 – 79		Acceptable	Passive
B-	72.6 – 74.0	65 – 69		Acceptable	Passive
C+	71.1 – 72.5	60 – 64	Good	Acceptable	Passive
C	65.0 – 71.0	41 – 59		Marginal	Passive
C-	62.7 – 64.9	35 – 40		Marginal	Passive
D	51.7 – 62.6	15 – 34	OK	Marginal	Detractor
E	25.1 – 51.6	2 – 14	Poor	Not Acceptable	Detractor
F	0 – 25	0 – 1.9	Worst Imaginable	Not Acceptable	Detractor

D. Usability Evaluation

The normalisation of System Usability Scale (SUS) scores to obtain percentile ranking makes the scores relevant. The raw and mean SUS score is 80.9 for the cybercrime monitoring system. It was normalised to a percentile ranking of 90. The percentile rank of 90 for the System was interpreted to be grade A. This indicates that the system was excellent and acceptable, and the users were promoters. Users won't dissuade others from utilising the proposed system as shown above.

E. Comparative Evaluation Analysis

The system has undergone a comparative analysis to determine its functionality, which is documented in Table 3; the graphical analysis of the system is shown by the bar chart in Figure 7. The study was compared with the Initial System and the result shows that the cybercrime monitoring system has an edge over the existing system.

Table 3: SUS Score for Cybercrime Monitoring System

Users	SUS Score (CMS)	SUS Initial System
1	87.5	70.0
2	80.0	72.5
3	80.0	75.0

4	82.5	80.0
5	87.5	72.5
6	77.5	77.5
7	87.5	70.0
8	82.5	70.0
9	75.0	72.5
10	72.5	77.5
11	77.5	80.0
12	75.0	75.0
13	82.5	70.0
14	75.0	72.5
15	80.0	77.5
16	82.5	70.0
17	85.0	72.5
18	82.5	70.0
19	82.0	75.0
20	82.5	80.0

From the result in Table 3, the raw and mean SUS score is 80.9 for the cybercrime monitoring system. It was normalised to a percentile ranking of 90. This indicates that the system was excellent and acceptable, and the users were promoters. The users will not deter others from utilising the proposed system while the mean SUS score for the initial system is 75.25 and was normalised to a percentile ranking of 72. This indicates

that the system was acceptable and the users were passive. The system's users will deter others from utilising it.

Figure 7: Graphical Representation of the Comparative Analysis

VI. CONCLUSION

Cyber security is a continual process that must be updated regularly. Network defenders are continuously fighting back as new applications and cybercriminals find and exploit new weaknesses in computer programmes and systems. The underlying ideas behind physical and general security also apply to cyber security. An evaluation of vulnerability kicks off the procedure. Risk evaluation, threat identification, findings documentation, and action plan development are all parts of vulnerability assessment. The vulnerability of the internet is one of the most serious threats to cyber security. Due to the use of email, online browsers, and other technologies, any web-based system has serious security problems. Governments across the world keep massive amounts of personal data and records on their residents, as well as sensitive government secrets, making them easy targets. Despite this, many government institutions face challenges such as inadequately secured infrastructure, a lack of awareness, and competing budget and resource objectives. Better security enables government agencies to deliver dependable services to the public, maintain citizen-to-government communications, safeguard sensitive information, and defend national security. Taking into consideration the increase in the rate of crimes using computers, one has to take every security measure to protect his cyberspace. This study contributes theoretically to the existing body of knowledge through a more extensive understanding of emerging technologies, with potential for future research. In addition, the system was executed at a minimal cost and reduces the difficulty of integrating a monitoring system into a website that will make individuals, organisations and government agencies find it easier to protect their websites effectively.

VII. SUGGESTED AREAS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

This work has been able to accomplish its objectives with certain observations noted. For future studies, the points below are proposed.

1. To combat cybercrime, you need to establish a special "cybercrime police" and train them on the use of information technology in cybercrime.
2. Cybersecurity education should be implemented at all

levels of education to educate Internet users and their outlook on the threats they may face when using the Internet.

3. Developers of hardware and software should provide technical remedies for typical cyber concerns in their new products.
4. All websites should include monitoring software for security checks against threats so that cyber police can identify and arrest criminals.
5. Organisations need to take strict security measures to protect their digital data.

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